

COMPOSITION OF THE CHOSEN LANDSCAPE PARKS OF THE 19th CENTURY IN SILESIA REGION OF POLAND

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The paper shows the composition of landscape parks founded in the 19th century in Silesia, the southern region of Poland. There were chosen three examples of parks representing different forms. All of them are residential, manorial or palace gardens. These types are the most popular. Their brief history is under discussion since the composition elements and changes go back to the beginning of the 20th century.

When telling about the composition of Silesian parks one should first of all discuss their general forms, functions and origin of adapted styles.

Forms of the 19th century parks in Silesia. Three types of composition dominated there. The landscape parks with the motives of natural origin closely connected with the environment, with sight axes and water system belong to the first type. The second type parks are of calligraphic configuration with dominating role of through alleys and paths interpenetrating with water elements. Such elements as hills, little bridges and various pavillions were very important. In the 19th century the complicated forms began gradually change for simple circular forms. Most small parks have such kind of composition. The third type park sare romantic, inspired by nostalgia for the by gone times, using historical forms of architecture, neo-styles and picturesque groups of plants, hills and water elements. Of course these types of composition are very often mixed together and it is difficult to decide which type is represented by a certain park.

Function of the 19th century parks in Silesia. When discussing the function of the

19th century parks it is important to mention four types. The first type parks are the large-scale objects. They connected a palace, which played the leading part, with a lot of different manors, farms, industrial objects, engineering facilities, etc. Most of them were designed at the same time and had a common road system, water system relative to view axes, being the structure of the integral composition filled with forests and fields. There are three such large-scale objects in Silesia: Dominion of Pszczyna (Pless Dominion), Dominion of Donnersmarck and Latifundium of Rudy (Rauden Latifundium).

The second type parks are connected with palaces, manors and residences. Being rather limited in size, they were places of rest for their owners. The amount of small architectural forms as well as the diversity of plants depended on the owner's prospetiry. These parks are the very point of this paper.

The third type parks are health resort parks of rest character, having special facilities and being closely connected with a sanatorium building. With development of industry some of these parks lost their function like Jastrzębie Zdrój and became the city parks, some of

them possess their own character and function even now like Goczałkowice Zdrój.

The city parks belong to the fourth type. They were founded early in the 19th century for all citizens of a town or for inhabitants of housing estate, they could also belong to an industrial enterprise. Some of them were founded in the enterprise territory. When creating these parks, the owners pursued the aim to make them the recreation and entertainment objects for citizens or workers. That was the policy of factory owners, since good living conditions helped them to attract good specialists and keep them long.

Origin of park styles in Silesia. Silesia has special character as a border region, divided for over hundreds of years between Russia, Austria and Germany. The region citizens were mostly Poles by birth but almost all factory owners were Germans. There were Czech and Hungarian influences too. Styles of the largest parks are referred to English or French models. The smaller parks took German or Austrian models. Austrian models were especially popular in the part governed by Russia.

Three parks were chosen as the objects of our research.

Park in Przyszowice. The oldest tree in the park, being about 250 years old, has remained from the period shown on the map compiled in 1736. Then the park owners were the Schimowski family (1734—1760 and 1791—1800), Werner family (1760—1791) and von Larisch (1800—1803). There was a manor during that time in Przyszowice. To the east of it there was a stream and behind it a big pond situated on the most part of the park territory. This pond was called "Schloss Teich" on the map of 1827. The stream ran northwards to the mill and a pond nearby. The ornamental park was spread northwards of the manor along the stream. North-west direction axis lead from the manor through a little pond and a courtyard to the church and then, dividing symmetrically the village, ended near the last houses nearby windmill. Place of that manor is occupied now by a later manor, a church and two roads of this composition are still clearly visible in the village. Von Larisch sold Przyszowice to Franz Galli, a merchant from Gliwice. Galli gave it to his

daughter Kathy and her husband Carl von Raczek. The village was their family property till 1927.

When analysing the age of the park trees it is possible to state that a big pond was liquidated there in 1860. After that there was founded the first landscape park with the area of about 10 ha. It is shown on the map of 1880. To the south and to the north of the manor, called then the "Schloss" (a castle), there were two courtyards surrounded by farm buildings. To the north of the castle there was the ornamental garden with a green-house. The composition axis joined the castle with the church and the rest of the village. One can see on the map two buildings in the mill neighbourhood. There lived a land-steward. The road system was not complicated. The main path lead through the park from the castle to the north-east, joining the outer road. The most interesting is the composition of trees in a form of a great spiral. It had to be very difficult to notice this shape from the ground. Maintained trees of that period are typical of native flora. The view axes were mainly opened from the park to the south-east, east and north. The park preserved such a form probably until the rebuilding of the castle in 1890. This composition elements allow stating that the mentioned park was of landscape-natural type.

After 1890 the road system was changed but most of new trees were planted between 1910 and 1930. This time already belongs to the 20th century and is out of our interest.

Park in Leszczyny. Leszczyny was a property of Laszowski family from 1701 up to the twenties of the 19th century. We do not know much about the composition of the park in that period. In the 30's and 40's of the 20th century the manor belonged to von Goertz. Age analysis of trees shows clear composition of this period. Trees, oaks, sycamore trees and elms formed two circles. The first one is big, with a diameter of about 70 m, the second circle is small with a diameter of about 30 m, joins the big one. The old oak is still preserved in the centre of the small circle. To the west of the circles there were a stream and a pond. It is difficult to tell which of the buildings shown on the map of 1882, is that mentioned in history as a wooden manor, which burned

down in 1895. There is no doubt that this manor was one of three buildings which stood near the southern part of the line of the trees forming the big circle. The manor could be that one, located on the axis of the road leading from the south. There were other buildings — stable, barn and some farm buildings around the cross-road to the north of that circle. It is impossible to say how the paths in the first half of the 20th century looked like. The circle of trees of that age enables to state that the park had a calligraphic style. Its area was about 2 ha.

There were three different owners in the manor for some years till 1865 when the manor was bought by Konrad Bartelt. He was being the owner up to the beginning of the 20th century. In 1882–83 a new palace was built in the centre of the big circle. This situation is shown on the map of 1882. To the south of the palace there were three buildings forming together a courtyard. The road from there was leading to the west. During that period such trees as oaks, maples, sycamores, limetree and elm were planted which completed the shape of the circles and formed another circle between the palace and a group of buildings around the courtyard. Near the entrance and the terrace *Acer platanoides* 'Schwedleri' was planted. On the east entrance axis there was planted *Tilia cordata*. Some kind of pedestal, probably used to stand cut flowers on it, stood in front of that entrance. On the axis on the other side *Acer pseudoplatanus* 'Purpureum' was planted. There was a small circle behind it. An erratic boulder is lying near the old oak in its centre now. In the place of the third circle there are other two boulders and three Ionic half-columns — romantic attributes, probably from the 19th century. The courtyard has lost its function after a fire, which destroyed the buildings in about 1895. There is no interpretation of the role of the axis leading from the palace to the north. There could be located an old ornamental garden or an alley. A conception of an ornamental garden does not fit to stable and barn distributed there. Probably it could be there before those buildings were built and probably led from the north to the wooden manor. All we

can say in conclusion is that the Leszczyny park composition during the whole 19th century kept calligraphic style.

Park in Promnice. Promnice is a part of the large-scale object: Dominion of Pszczyna (Pless Dominion). The history of Pszczyna goes back to the 10th century. The owners of Pszczyna were Poles, Czechs, Hungarians and Germans by birth. The territory which belonged to the dominion had a status of the duchy. The name of Promnice comes from Promnic family — the owners between 1548 and 1765. Next owners were Anhalt family. Friedrich Erdmann von Anhalt built a dam on the Gostynka river in 1796, thus the Paprocańskie lake came into being. In 1847 Heinrich von Anhalt gave the estate his nephew Johann Heinrich XI Hochberg. The estate belonged to the family of Hochberg until the thirties of the 19th century. The Hunting Castle in Promnice was built in 1861. It was designed by Olivier Pavelt in Neo-Gothic style. The Hunting Castle was the hunting manor for the duke and his friends. Visitors of the castle were tsar Alexander, the emperor of Austria and the king of Prussia. The castle was founded on a little hill near the Paprocańskie lake bank. There were four periods of the history of its surrounding. The first one is connected with the specific hunting function. In that period the castle stood among the group of oaks. There was a zone free of trees between that group and the forest border. That enabled admiring its romantic form and secured good view from the castle to observe wild animals. During that time there were only native trees there. Near the castle behind an elm line there were built a stable, a barn and a forester's lodge, all in Neo-Gothic style. The area of that surrounding was about 2 ha. The second period, when Princess Daisy lived in the castle, brought the lime alley. Then, *Tsuga canadensis* was planted near the cross-road. Other changes appeared already in the 19th century, when the family of Hochberg von Pless decided to plant there more introduced trees. A picturesque castle, other buildings and surroundings manifest roman character of the residence and the park around.

Thus, the three chosen parks represent three basic styles typical of Silesian landscape

design in the 19th century. They are the parks of the temperate area. The main buildings in a form of a palace, manor and residence show all forms present in Silesia. In spite of some elements their style types are clearly readable and representative. The given work shows the method of analysis of the park historical value. Having this information we can decide which period brings the highest value and what elements we have to preserve.

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СКЛАД ДЕЯКИХ ЛАНДШАФТНИХ ПАРКІВ СИЛЕЗІЇ, ЗАСНОВАНИХ У ХІХ сторіччі

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Показано склад ландшафтних парків, заснованих у ХІХ ст. у Силезії (південний регіон Польщі). Досліджено

три найпопулярніші типи парків, що представляють різні форми, проте є резидентними, маноріальними або палацовими садами. Обговорюється коротка хронологія парків з позицій їх елементного складу та змін, які виникли на початку ХХ ст.

СОСТАВ НЕКОТОРЫХ ЛАНДШАФТНЫХ ПАРКОВ СИЛЕЗИИ, ОСНОВАННЫХ В ХІХ веке

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Показан состав ландшафтных парков, основанных в ХІХ в. в Силезии (южный регион Польши). Исследованы три наиболее популярных типа парков, представляющих различные формы, однако являющихся резидентными, маноріальными или дворцовыми садами. Обсуждается краткая хронология парков с позиций их элементного состава и изменений, возникших к началу ХХ в.

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ВПЛИВ ФІЗІОЛОГІЧНО АКТИВНИХ РЕЧОВИН АУКСИНОВОЇ ПРИРОДИ НА РИЗОГЕННУ АКТИВНІСТЬ СТЕБЛОВИХ ЖИВЦІВ LONICERA EDULIS TURCZ. І CORNUS MAS L.

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Наведено результати вивчення впливу фізіологічно активних речовин ауксинової природи на регенераційну здатність стеблових живців *Lonicera edulis Turcz.* і *Cornus mas L.* Встановлено, що ризогенна активність у живців залежить від впливу фізіологічно активних речовин ауксинової природи, їх метамерності, строків живцювання і умов укорінювання.

Особливий інтерес для впровадження у виробництво викликають такі садові культури, як жимолость їстівна (*Lonicera edulis Turcz.*) та дерен звичайний (*Cornus mas L.*). Ці рослини являють собою джерела вітамінів, пло-

ди мають в собі цінні лікувальні біологічно активні властивості, чим заслуговують на широке розповсюдження [3, 4, 7].

Прискоренню вирощування саджанців жимолості та дерену значною мірою сприяє кореневласне розмноження стебловими живцями, що оснований на репродуктивній ре-

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